

ASSESSING THE EFFECT OF ELECTRONIC TAX SYSTEMS ON TAX COMPLIANCE AMONG SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES IN BENUE STATE

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the effect of electronic tax systems on tax compliance among small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Benue State, Nigeria. The primary objectives were to assess the effect of digital tools like Point of Sale (POS) systems, E-filing systems, Electronic Payment Portals (EPP), and the Tax Identification Number (TIN) on tax compliance by SMEs. The research employed a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative data from structured questionnaires with qualitative information gathered through semi-structured interviews. A sample of 196 SMEs were selected using stratified random sampling to ensure proportional representation across different income levels and locations within Benue State. The quantitative data were analyzed using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression to determine the relationships between electronic tax systems and tax compliance. The findings of the study reveal that electronic tax systems have a substantial positive impact on tax compliance by SMEs in Benue State. The adoption of POS systems improved the accuracy and transparency of tax records, making it easier for SMEs to track transactions and remit taxes. The study also found that E-filing systems contributed to a higher rate of timely tax submissions, as businesses appreciated the convenience and reduced administrative burden associated with online filing. The user-friendliness of the E-filing system allowed SMEs to navigate the process more efficiently, thus encouraging compliance. Additionally, the Electronic Payment Portal (EPP) and the use of TIN was found to significantly improve the level of tax compliance. It was concluded that the implementation of electronic tax systems has a positive effect on tax compliance among SMEs in Benue State. The study recommends that the Benue State Internal Revenue Service (BIRS) should focus on improving digital infrastructure and increasing awareness campaigns to further enhance the adoption of electronic tax systems by SMEs, thereby boosting compliance rates and improving revenue generation for the state.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the adoption of electronic tax systems has emerged as a strategic response by governments to enhance tax administration, improve compliance, and broaden the tax base. Nigeria, like many developing countries, has embraced these systems in a bid to modernize its tax collection processes and reduce the inefficiencies associated with manual procedures (Yua Ityavyar and Yua, (2023). In this framework, the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) and the Benue State Internal Revenue Service (BIRS) have implemented various electronic platforms aimed at simplifying tax registration, filing, and payment (Lanem, Yua, & Upaa , 2020).

Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) play a significant role in Nigeria's economy, contributing to job creation, poverty reduction, and economic diversification (Gbemisola, Ayotunde, Yua, and Oluwaseun (2022). Despite their economic importance, tax compliance levels among SMEs are notoriously low. According to the Nigerian Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2019), as of 2018, Nigeria had over 69.5 million employed individuals, yet only 19 million were registered taxpayers. This indicates a significant portion of the working population, many of whom operate SMEs, remain outside the formal tax net (Itavyar & Yua 2023).

Electronic tax systems, such as online tax filing platforms, have been recognized for their role in enhancing transparency within the tax administration process. These systems provide SMEs with clear guidelines on tax liabilities and deadlines, making the overall tax environment more navigable. By reducing ambiguity in tax requirements, electronic systems enable businesses to understand their obligations more thoroughly, which encourages higher compliance rates. Studies have shown that the use of information and communication technology (ICT) tools, such as electronic systems, has a positive impact on voluntary compliance, as they simplify the complex processes traditionally associated with tax filing (Lubua, 2014; Kiringa & Jagongo, 2017; Ali, Nwakoby, Okonkwo, & Yua, 2020). By reducing the administrative burden on both businesses and tax authorities, electronic systems facilitate smoother and more efficient compliance, fostering a more cooperative relationship between SMEs and tax regulators.

Further research shows the persistent issue of low tax compliance among SMEs in Nigeria, particularly at the state level. The Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS, 2020) reported that SMEs often evade taxes due to factors such as the complexity of the tax system, the cost of compliance, and mistrust in tax authorities (Ajekwe, Yua, Epor & Victor, 2024). In Benue State, where this study is focused, the compliance gap is similarly alarming, with less than 10% of SMEs reportedly adhering to their tax obligations (Benue State Inland Revenue Service, 2021). This low compliance level has serious implications for the state's revenue generation and its ability to fund development projects. The low tax compliance levels among SMEs in Nigeria have significant implications. First, it undermines the ability of the government to generate sufficient revenue for public services. According to the World Bank (2022), Nigeria's tax-to-GDP ratio of 6.0% is one of the lowest in Africa, well below the continental average of 16.6%. The poor tax compliance rates among SMEs contribute significantly to this shortfall. As a result, the government is forced to rely heavily on external borrowing, exacerbating the country's debt burden and limiting its fiscal space.

In addition to revenue loss, non-compliance increases the cost of tax administration. The enforcement actions required to ensure compliance, such as audits and litigation, are resource-intensive and often yield limited results. Non-compliance also creates inequity within the tax system, where compliant taxpayers bear a disproportionate burden compared

to those who evade taxes. This erodes trust in the tax system and can further discourage compliance. Moreover, the persistence of low compliance rates can create an environment that fosters corruption and tax fraud. As noted by the Chartered Institute of Taxation of Nigeria (CITN, 2021), tax fraud is often facilitated by manual tax administration processes, which provide opportunities for corrupt practices such as tax evasion and underreporting of income.

Recognizing the challenges posed by low tax compliance, the Nigerian government has implemented a series of tax reforms aimed at improving tax administration and increasing compliance, particularly among SMEs (Epor, Yua & Nwakoby, 2023). One of the most significant reforms has been the introduction of electronic tax systems. This reform aligns with recommendations from international bodies such as the International Monetary Fund (IMF), which emphasized in a 2007 report that electronic tax administration systems are essential for ensuring transparency and detecting fraudulent practices. According to the IMF Institute and Fiscal Affairs Department (2007), electronic systems offer real-time data on tax liabilities and payments, which helps reduce opportunities for tax evasion and improves overall compliance.

In Nigeria, the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) launched the Integrated Tax Administration System (ITAS) in 2013 as part of a broader effort to modernize the tax system. ITAS allows taxpayers to register, file, and pay taxes online, providing a more efficient and transparent platform for tax administration. Additionally, the Taxpayer Identification Number (TIN) system was introduced to track taxpayers and reduce fraud, while the e-filing system facilitates the timely submission of tax returns. At the state level, Benue State has also implemented several electronic tax administration reforms, including the introduction of point-of-sale (POS) systems for tax payments and an online tax portal for e-filing. These initiatives are designed to make it easier for SMEs to comply with their tax obligations and to reduce the costs associated with compliance (Yua, Ogohi, & Epor, 2022; Ejinkonye, Yua, Nwanko & Mbanefo, 2023).

Despite the progress in tax digitalization, there remains a notable gap in understanding the specific factors that influence the tax compliance of SMEs in Benue State. Existing literature largely overlooks the local challenges that SMEs face in adopting electronic tax systems, such as limited technical literacy, mistrust in digital platforms, and perceived complexity of the e-filing process. This study therefore aims to fill these gaps by investigating the effect of electronic tax systems on tax compliance among SMEs in Benue State, Nigeria by assessing the impact of various components of the digital tax system, such as the POS system, e-filing, and the TIN, on tax compliance in the state.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

2.1.3 The optimal tax theory

Slemrod (1990) Slemrod's optimal tax theory focuses on designing and implementing a tax system that minimizes inefficiency and distortion in the market under economic constraints. It considers individuals' utility and technology in tax collection, aiming to avoid distortion and inefficiency. Tax literature should focus on tax collection technology and economic factors affecting tax collection. Theorists should understand real constraints and objectives before offering pre-cut solutions. The main objective of electronic tax administration is to achieve effective and efficient tax processes.

2.2 Conceptual Framework

2.2.1 Small and Medium Scale Enterprise (SMEs)

Small and medium enterprises (SME) were introduced in the late 1940s to improve trade and industrialization in developed nations. Definitions vary by country and are based on their role in the economy, policies, and programs. Quantitative definitions include monetary terms like turnover, asset value, and profit, while qualitative ones include the number of employees. The Central Bank of Nigeria defines a SME as any enterprise with a maximum asset base of N1.5 billion. SMEs are classified based on their total cost, including working capital, and the size of their business. Micro enterprises have a low cost, while small enterprises have higher costs and resources. Medium enterprises have more capital and can operate on a larger scale. Small enterprises serve a larger customer base and have formal business structures, while medium enterprises have broader markets and significant economic impact. The Central Bank of Nigeria's 2005 guideline on SMEIS defines SME as an enterprise with a maximum asset base of 200 million naira, excluding land and working capital.

2.2.2 Overview of Taxation System in Nigeria

The structure of the Nigerian tax system primarily serves as a mechanism for raising money. This has mostly remained unchanged since its introduction and is a holdover from the pre-independence government's use of 1948 British tax legislation. The Income Tax Management Act (ITMA) of 1961 was a response to the national necessity to tax personal incomes. Pay as you earn (PAYE) is the foundation for personal income tax (PIT) in salaried work in Nigeria. The 1961 ITMA Act has undergone multiple changes. For example, PIT climbed to N2000 plus 12.5% of income over N6000 in 1985 from N600, or 10% of earned income. In 1989, the tax on rental income was expanded to include chartered vessels, ships, and aircraft, and a 15 percent withholding tax was imposed on savings accounts worth N50000 or more. Furthermore, a 15 percent tax was imposed on the fees paid to directors. These policies were designed to protect local industry effectively, increase the use of raw materials, and increase government revenue, among other goals (Ezenagu, 2019). As a result, emphasis has been placed on encouraging manufacturing exports and lowering personal and corporate tax burdens. To align with this shift in policy priorities, numerous actions were carried out. These included, among other things, evaluating the capital allowances for rebats and custom exemptions, extending the duty drawback program, manufacturing-in-blood, and eliminating excise duty. Implementing the Value Added Tax (VAT), monetizing termination benefits, and providing lower-income earners with more tax relief.

2.2.3 Challenges Faced by the Nigerian Tax System

Numerous issues plague the Nigerian tax system; a few of these are listed below;

- **Lack of tax figures:** Taxes, the oldest governmental activity in Nigeria, are not easily accessible due to significant data management shortcomings in state agencies and federal tax offices, except Delta, Lagos, Kaduna, Katsina, and Nigeria Customs Services (Lanem, Yua, & Upaa, 2020). This lack of data accessibility hinders policy-making and hinders data collection and analysis.
- **Inability to prioritize tax effort:** Nigeria's political economy prioritizes state parity, pollution, land area, social development, and internal revenue generation over tax efforts. This approach heavily relies on erratic oil revenues, affecting government levels and

inhibiting proactive revenue drives. Despite some state governments enhancing tax generation efforts, no serious effort has been made to strengthen taxing rules.

- **Inadequate tax administration:** Tax administration faces challenges due to shortages of personnel, funds, equipment, and supplies. Low compensation and motivation contribute to unfavorable attitudes towards taxpayers. The Nigerian government faces difficulties in increasing revenue due to lack of administrative ability. Only 12.6% of the federal inland revenue service staff are tax professionals, and municipal government staff lack frequent training, resulting in inadequate tax administration coverage and assessment.
- **Tax multiplicity:** One of the main issues the nation is currently confronting is the tax multiplicity. People and corporate entities express dissatisfaction with the cascading consequences of tax duplication; this issue originated from state grievances against the inconsistency between their fiscal authorities and their fiscal duties (Etim, 2020). Certain states decided to impose certain taxes as recompense, which has resulted in arbitrary actions, intimidation, and even business closures. To address this uncomfortable circumstance, the 1998 Taxes and Levies Act was passed.
- **Regulatory difficulties:** Nigeria faces significant business and regulatory challenges due to political risk, exchange controls, IP protection, and company law. Unlike first-world countries, Nigeria's shifting political regimes can lead to company loss or inability to remit profits.
- **Economic structural issues:** Nigeria has transitioned from direct to indirect taxes since the early 1990s due to perceived less distortion. VAT, applied on value-added goods, is less likely to generate distortion. However, structural issues in the economy limit the benefits of this taxation, with the informal sector dominating domestic output and posing risks for income tax. Effective methods for collecting personal income tax and VAT from self-employed individuals are still undeveloped. The extent of these taxes' application depends on economic development rate.
- **Economy of the underworld:** The hidden economy refers to economic activities not publicly disclosed, including businesses required to pay taxes but not, individuals operating in the shadow economy, and those reporting certain incomes but not others. The expansion of Nigeria's black market economy could lead to policy concerns, as higher tax rates may encourage tax evasion, draining income and necessitating higher tax rates in areas with evasion. The shadow economy can taint official economic growth estimates and lead to poor policy decisions. Therefore, considering the underground economy is crucial when forecasting tax changes.

2.2.4 Electronic tax administration and systems

Automation, a process of using machines to perform tasks, is essential for accurate, efficient, and effective tax administration. It allows data entry, automated processing, computation, analysis, and automatic production of tax reports. An e-tax system provides a secure, 24/7 self-service option for taxpayers, offering registration, filing, payment, education, and information, without requiring intervention from tax administration staff.

2.2.5 Nigeria's electronic tax system

The Integrated Tax Administration system (ITAS) was launched in Nigeria in 2013 to automate tax administration, simplify processes, and promote voluntary compliance. The

software is designed for emerging nations seeking electronic control over state money. The system aims to simplify procedures, ensure transparency, re-engineer service delivery, minimize administrative costs, improve voluntary tax compliance, and provide consistent, high-quality service to all taxpayers. It also offers a comprehensive taxpayer information repository for FIRS to oversee taxpayers throughout their lifecycle. The ITAS system supports three languages, enabling tax agents to communicate with taxpayers in their preferred language. It supports various tax types, including income, VAT, sales, and property taxes, aiming to increase tax collection and reduce system leakages.

2.2.6 Tax compliance

Tax compliance is defined as the full payment of all taxes due (Braithwaite, 2009). Tax non-compliance refers to the difference between actual taxes paid and due, often due to overstatement or understatement of income, expenses, and deductions, and can be intentional or unintentional, involving calculation errors and inadequate understanding of tax laws.

According to Jones (2009) Tax compliance involves timely filing, reporting, and payment of tax information, self-assessment, and payment without enforcement action. It consists of three dimensions: filing compliance, reporting compliance, and payment compliance. Non-compliant taxpayers fail in these dimensions. Modern information technology has revolutionized tax administration, making it easier for citizens to pay taxes without hassle. This has significantly impacted fiscal systems and taxation. Tax compliance is achieved when taxpayers voluntarily file returns and pay taxes without authorities' intervention. Three theoretical perspectives measure compliance: economic models, uncertainty models, norms of compliance models, and inertia models.

2.2.7 Quality of electronic system on tax compliance

The quality of an information system, including hardware and software, significantly impacts user satisfaction and taxpayer compliance. A reliable, user-friendly system with easy payment options and a variety of tax services boosts voluntary tax compliance. However, some SMEs may resist adopting technology due to poor system quality, leading to low tax compliance. For example, Kenyan taxpayers feel uncomfortable using electronic tax systems compared to manual ones, indicating that poor system quality can hinder adoption and negatively impact tax compliance.

The stability of a taxation system during peak times is crucial for its quality. System hang-ups can lead to delays in tax return submissions, causing taxpayers to postpone their filings. Additionally, system hang-ups can cause SMEs to outsource services to specialized cyber cafes, incurring costs to pay third parties to file on their behalf. This compromise of information can compromise the accuracy of the submitted returns. The quality of services provided to taxpayers is also crucial. E-tax systems improve tax compliance by facilitating faster accessibility to tax services without physical visits, enabling timely filing and reporting of required tax information. The quality of information also shortens the time taken to extract data, enter tax return data, match returns against filing requirements, process tax payments, and issue assessments and refunds, simplifying tax processes and making it easier for taxpayers to comply.

2.2.8 Technology literacy on tax compliance

Taxpayer education is crucial for SMEs to comply with tax matters and create positive attitudes towards tax compliance. Technology literacy, such as internet usage and basic

computer troubleshooting skills, is essential for adopting electronic tax systems. Employees with computer skills find the e-tax system pleasant and efficient, leading to increased tax compliance. However, low educational levels among employees can hinder the use of electronic filing devices and negatively impact tax compliance. Tax authorities should focus on increasing electronic tax system usage and providing further training on tax compliance. Customized education programs, targeted at newly incorporated companies and SMEs not represented by tax agents, can help educate taxpayers on existing tax rules and new tax changes.

2.2.9 Technology security concerns on tax compliance

Taxpayer education is crucial for SMEs to comply with tax matters and create positive attitudes towards tax compliance. Technology literacy, such as internet usage and basic computer troubleshooting skills, is essential for adopting electronic tax systems. Employees with computer skills find the e-tax system pleasant and efficient, leading to increased tax compliance. However, low educational levels among employees can hinder the use of electronic filing devices and negatively impact tax compliance. Tax authorities should focus on increasing electronic tax system usage and providing further training on tax compliance. Customized education programs, targeted at newly incorporated companies and SMEs not represented by tax agents, can help educate taxpayers on existing tax rules and new tax changes.

2.2.10 System development methodologies

Software development methodologies involve a systematic approach to creating information systems, requiring a stepwise creation cycle. Examples include prototyping, waterfall, rapid application development, and iterative and incremental approaches. The Waterfall model, inspired by older engineering disciplines, was chosen for the E-taxation system. These methodologies define deliverables for project teams.

2.2.11 Electronic tax payment portal

The e-tax payment portal allows taxpayers to pay direct taxes online, eliminating the need for cash transactions and cashiers. This facility is particularly useful for those who prefer to pay at commercial banks, which can be complicated and error-prone. iTAX streamlines communication between taxpayers, commercial banks, and the tax authority using the same "Payment Posting" screen. Future development plans include integrating mobile payment services with mobile service providers, allowing small payments to be made through mobile phones.

2.2.12 Electronic cash register

An e-cash register is a pre-programmed device that tracks and records cash transactions for individuals and businesses. It includes functions like sales calculation, price look-ups, and receipt printing. Basic models include keyboards, display units, and printers. Advanced models require separate software programs. E-cash registers are secure, locking the cash drawer for authorized users.

2.2.13 Use of point of sales (POS) for tax collection

Point of Sales (POS) refers to the hardware and software used for checkouts in various retail businesses, including supermarkets, restaurants, hotels, and stadiums. POS systems have evolved from mechanical cash registers to electrical cash registers, with the first computer-based system introduced in 1973. POS systems have evolved to handle multiple

applications, including credit card processing, gift card activation, age verification, and employee time tracking. Most retail POS systems include integrated accounting, inventory management, purchasing demand forecasting, customer relationship management, service management, leasing, and payroll modules. Large retailers use standardized interfaces to standardize electronic systems and simplify interconnecting. In the restaurant industry, POS systems are used in fast food service and sales chains, with virtual computers and touch screens connected to a server. (Tikapichart and Smith, 2018).

2.2.14 Challenges of Using the Electronic Tax System

Dowe (2008) The implementation of e-filing and e-payment systems requires a reliable internet service, cooperative financial institutions, an IT-oriented public, and adequate financing for infrastructure in tax offices. A comprehensive IT design, development, and implementation strategy should be developed for successful implementation. Many countries have taken a gradual approach, allowing voluntary E-filing and e-payment for select taxpayer segments in the initial stages. However, challenges such as intermittent power supply and internet outages have been reported in Uganda.

The iTax system, hosted on a central server, lacks historical records of taxpayers and is a "going forward" type, only storing tax records from the time of registering for iTax onwards. Employees play a vital role in ensuring revenue authority collection and client knowledge of business taxation. Low integrity among employees affects efforts to improve revenue collection.

The use of ICTs for self-assessment addresses the challenge of employee integrity and promotes voluntary compliance. Training is essential to provide clients with the skills necessary to raise their attitude towards voluntary tax compliance. In Tanzania, employees organize seminars to educate stakeholders about voluntary tax compliance benefits, but many respondents admit to never receiving training from tax officers due to inadequate staff.

2.3 Review of Empirical Studies

Eilu (2018), in a study titled *Adoption of Electronic Fiscal Devices and VAT Compliance in East Africa*, explored the effectiveness of electronic fiscal devices (EFDs) in improving VAT compliance across Kenya, Tanzania, and Uganda. Using a mixed-method approach that combined surveys and interviews with tax officials and SMEs, Eilu analyzed compliance rates before and after EFD adoption. The findings indicated that EFDs led to a 20% increase in VAT collections in Kenya and Tanzania over three years, but Uganda faced challenges such as low awareness and inadequate training, which limited the effectiveness of EFDs. Eilu concluded that technological interventions like EFDs require robust user education and integration into existing tax frameworks to yield optimal results.

Felix and Cyrus (2020) conducted a study titled *Digital Cargo Tracking Systems and Revenue Collection in Kenya* to assess the impact of digital systems on revenue transparency and compliance. The research used a case study design, focusing on the Kenya Revenue Authority's (KRA) implementation of digital cargo tracking. Data collection involved interviews with KRA officials and analysis of revenue records over a five-year period. The study revealed that the tracking system significantly enhanced transparency, reducing smuggling and underreporting, which led to a 15% increase in tax revenues from cargo. The authors emphasized that digital systems can substantially improve compliance if they are well-monitored and integrated within the revenue collection processes.

Irefe-Esema and Akinmade (2020) studied the *Impact of E-Filing on Tax Compliance Among SMEs in Nigeria*, focusing on how digital systems influence compliance behavior. Their research involved a cross-sectional survey of 200 SMEs in Lagos, using structured questionnaires to assess their experiences with the e-filing system. The data were analyzed using regression analysis to understand the relationship between e-filing adoption and compliance. Results showed a strong positive correlation, with 78% of respondents indicating that e-filing simplified tax processes and reduced compliance costs, resulting in a 25% increase in compliance rates. The authors concluded that digitalization enhances record accuracy and simplifies compliance, particularly for small businesses.

Mugo (2019) examined the *Electronic Filing and Compliance Behavior: Evidence from South Africa* to evaluate the impact of e-filing on taxpayer behavior. The study adopted a longitudinal research design, analyzing data from the South African Revenue Service (SARS) over five years before and after the introduction of the e-filing system. Interviews with SARS officials provided qualitative insights into the challenges and successes of the e-filing rollout. The findings showed a significant improvement in on-time tax filings, rising from 60% to 85% after e-filing was introduced. However, Mugo identified initial resistance from taxpayers and system outages as challenges that needed continuous system updates for sustained compliance improvements.

Awai and Oboh (2020) analyzed the *Effectiveness of POS Systems in Enhancing Revenue Collection in Nigeria* through a survey of 150 tax officials and SMEs in Lagos and Benue states. The study utilized descriptive statistics and chi-square tests to explore the relationship between the use of POS systems and tax compliance. Findings highlighted that POS systems contributed to a 30% reduction in payment defaults as they enabled real-time tax remittance. Tax officials also reported a decrease in late payments and discrepancies. However, the study noted that network reliability remained a key challenge in ensuring the seamless operation of POS systems, particularly in rural areas.

Nkote and Luwuga (2010) conducted a study on *POS-Based Tax Collection Systems in Uganda*, focusing on the Uganda Revenue Authority's (URA) use of POS systems to improve tax compliance. Using a case study approach, the researchers gathered data through interviews with URA officials and focus group discussions with SMEs, alongside analysis of tax collection records from 2008 to 2010. The findings showed that POS systems significantly reduced the average time for tax remittance by 40%, thereby increasing compliance among SMEs. However, the study identified geographic disparities in access to POS terminals, suggesting a need for broader distribution to enhance their effectiveness.

Olurankinse and Oladeji (2018), in their research titled *The Role of Taxpayer Identification Numbers in Reducing Tax Evasion in Nigeria*, examined the effectiveness of the TIN system in tracking compliance among SMEs. The study employed a quasi-experimental design, comparing tax compliance rates before and after TIN implementation in three Nigerian states—Lagos, Benue, and Anambra. Data were collected through archival tax records and structured interviews with tax officials. The results indicated that the introduction of TIN systems reduced multiple filings and tax evasion cases, leading to a 15% increase in revenue. Despite these benefits, the authors highlighted challenges in the integration of TIN databases across states, leading to occasional discrepancies in taxpayer records.

Adu-Gyamfi and Osei (2019) explored the *Impact of Unique Taxpayer Identification on Tax Compliance in Ghana* using a mixed-methods approach. Their study involved surveys of 300 SMEs and interviews with Ghana Revenue Authority officials to assess the effectiveness of TIN systems. The analysis compared compliance rates before and after the

system's implementation. The findings revealed a 20% increase in registered taxpayers, attributed to enhanced transparency and traceability of tax records through TIN. However, the authors noted that ongoing public education and training were necessary to maximize the potential of the TIN system, as many SMEs initially struggled with the registration process.

Seelmann *et al.* (2010) studied *Barriers to the Adoption of Electronic Tax Systems in Developing Economies* with a focus on challenges faced by countries like Tanzania, Ghana, and Nigeria. Using a qualitative approach, the researchers conducted in-depth interviews with tax officials and SMEs to understand the barriers to digital tax adoption. Their findings identified inadequate internet infrastructure and low levels of digital literacy as the main barriers, which led to slow uptake of e-filing and digital payment platforms. They also observed that in areas where digital infrastructure was improved, compliance rates increased by up to 18%, highlighting the importance of targeted investments in technology and taxpayer education.

Lubua (2014) investigated the *Role of User Training in the Success of E-Tax Systems* in Tanzania, using a case study of the Tanzanian Revenue Authority's e-tax platform. Data collection included surveys with 150 SME owners and interviews with 20 tax officials. Lubua found that lack of user training and technical support was a significant barrier to the effective adoption of e-tax systems. The study revealed that SMEs that received training were 35% more likely to comply with their tax obligations compared to those without such support. The study emphasized the importance of regular training programs to improve the adoption and effective use of digital tax systems.

Zayol and Gberindyer (2018) conducted a comparative study titled *Digitalization of Tax Administration: A Comparative Study of Lagos and Benue States*. This study used a mixed-methods approach, combining surveys of SMEs and interviews with tax officials in both states, alongside an analysis of tax revenue records from 2015 to 2018. The research found that Lagos, with better digital infrastructure, recorded higher compliance rates than Benue State. Although Benue's adoption of digital tools like POS and e-filing led to a 12% increase in compliance, it lagged behind Lagos due to issues such as poor system integration and low awareness among SMEs. The study highlighted the need for more robust public education campaigns and technical improvements to maximize the benefits of digital tax systems in Benue.

3.0

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The research design adopted for this study is the survey research. According to Akpa (2011), a survey design is characterized by the researcher reaching out to the respondents in their natural setting to collect data from them, by asking questions via fill-out questionnaire, personal interview or telephone interview or both, processing and analyzing the collected data. This method of research design is deemed to be more appropriate for the topic under discussion because the data is with taxpayers and tax administrators and not in any documented form.

3.7 Model Specification

The model for the study is as follows:

$$TCOMP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 POS + \beta_2 TIN + \beta_3 EFS + \beta_4 EPP + E$$

Where,

TCOMP = Tax Compliance

EFS = Electronic Filing System.

POS = Point of Sale.

TIN = Tax Identification Number.

EPP = Electronic Payment Portal.

E = Error term

β_0 = Constant

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ = the coefficient of the dependent variables

3.8 Method of Data Analysis

The data collected was transferred into the STATA software for analysis. The OLS regression analysis was used as the major technique for data analysis. The OLS regression technique was used to determine the relationship between the dependent and the independent variables identified. The t-test obtained from the regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses that were formulated.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This study sought to examine the effect of electronic tax system on tax compliance by SMEs in Benue State, Nigeria. This section presents result of findings and discussions.

4.1 Data Presentation

Figure 1 shows the age of respondents. Out of 196 respondents, 29 students representing 15 % were between the age range of 18 - 24 years. 119 (61 %) respondents were between 25 – 59 years old while 47 respondents (24 %) were 60 year and above. Majority of the respondents were within the age group of 25 – 29 years.

Figure 1: Age composition of the Respondents,**Source: STATA, 2025.****Table 1: POS and Tax Compliance**

No	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	UD	Total
1	The POS system introduced by BIRS will improve the tracking of taxpayer's record.	101(51.5)	50(25.5)	20(10.2)	10(5.1)	15(7.7)	196
2	The payment of tax through POS system will serve as a means of promoting openness and honesty of the taxpayers.	51(26.0)	100(51.0)	10(5.1)	15(7.7)	20(10.2)	196
3	The payment of tax through POS system will serve as more credible means of tax compliance by SMEs in Benue State.	112(57.1)	60(30.6)	5(2.6)	3(1.5)	16(8.2)	196
4	The payment of tax through POS system is characterized by accuracy and clarity and provide for easy compilation of tax figures and timely remittances of taxes.	86(43.9)	54(27.6)	28(14.3)	17(8.7)	11(5.6)	196
5	The POS system adopted by small and medium scale enterprises has help tax compliance in Benue State.	92(47.0)	43(22.0)	22(11.2)	14(7.1)	25(12.8)	196
	Total	442	307	85	59	86	980
	Average	88.4	61.4	17.0	11.8	17.2	196

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 presents information on Point of Sales (POS) system. From the table item 1 shows that out of 196 respondents, 101 respondents representing 51.5% strongly agreed, 50 respondents (25.5 %) agreed, 20 respondents representing 10.2 % disagreed. Only 5.1 % of the respondents further strongly disagreed while 15 respondents (7.7 %) were undecided on the view that the POS system introduced by BIRS will improve the tracking of taxpayer's records. On item 2, 26 % of respondents strongly agreed, 100 respondents representing 51 % agreed, 10 respondents disagreed while 15 respondents representing 7.7 % strongly disagreed and 20 respondents were undecided on the view that the payment of tax through POS system will serve as a means of promoting openness and honesty of the taxpayers. Furthermore, item 3 indicates 5 respondents disagreed, 3 respondents strongly disagreed,

representing 1.5 % and 2.6 % respectively. Only 15 respondents were undecided on the statement that the payment of tax through POS system will serve as more credible means of tax compliance among SMEs in Benue state. However, 112 respondents (57 %) strongly agreed with the statement while 60 respondents agreed while.

A total of 86 respondents representing 43.9 % on item 4 strongly agreed, 54 respondents agreed, and 28 respondents disagreed while 17 respondents representing 8.7 % strongly disagree. In addition, on this same item, 11 respondents (5.6 %) were undecided on the view that payment of tax through POS system is characterized by tax accuracy and clarity and provide for easy compilation of tax figures and timely remittances of taxes. Finally, item 5 of the table indicates that 92 respondents representing 47 % strongly agreed, 43 respondents agreed, while 22 respondents disagreed. Out of the respondents on the same item, 14 of them strongly disagreed while 25 respondents were undecided on the statement that the POS system adopted by Small and Medium Scale Enterprises has help tax compliance in Benue state.

Table 2: E-Filing System and Tax Compliance

No	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	UD	Total
6	The e-tax filing system introduced by BIRS has compelled all SMEs to file their returns online within the required time.	96(49)	55(28.1)	7(3.6)	30(15.3)	8(4.1)	196
7	The e-tax filing system provides a more accurate basis of assessing taxpayer's records, making it easier to get hold of tax evaders.	60(30.6)	108(55.10)	10(5.1)	12(6.1)	6(3.1)	196
8	The introduction of the e-tax filing by the BIRS will build more confidence in taxpayers in Benue State. Thus, boosting their morale to comply with their statutory obligation of paying taxes.	39(19.9)	121(61.7)	17(8.70)	5(2.6)	14(7.1)	196
9	The e-tax filing is less prone to manipulations, and its adoption will help curb tax evasion.	83(42.3)	45(23)	24(12.2)	19(9.7)	25(12.8)	196
10	The e-filing introduced by Benue State Inland Revenue Service (BIRS) has impacted positively on tax compliance in Benue State.	106(54.1)	59(30.1)	14(7.1)	12(6.1)	5(2.6)	196
Total		384	388	72	78	58	980
Average		76.8	77.6	14.4	15.6	11.6	196

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 2 shows information on Electronic Filing (E-filing). From the table item 6 shows that out of 196 respondents, 96 respondents representing 49 % strongly agreed, 55 respondents (28.1 %) agreed, 7 respondents disagreed. Only 30 respondents representing 15.3 % further strongly disagreed while 8 respondents (4.1 %) were undecided on the view that the E-tax filing system introduced by BIRS has compelled all SME's to file their returns online within the required time. On item 7, 60 respondents representing 30.6 % strongly agreed, 108 respondents (55.1 %) agreed, 10 respondents (5.1 %) disagreed. Also, 12 respondents representing 6.1 % further strongly disagreed while 6 respondents (3.1 %) were undecided on the view that the E-tax filing system will provide a more accurate basis of assessing taxpayers' records, making it easier to get hold of tax evaders. Furthermore, item 8 shows that 39 respondents (19.9 %) strongly agreed, 121 respondents representing 61.7 % agreed while 17 respondents (8.7 %) disagreed with the statement. However, on this same item, 5 respondents representing 2.6 % strongly disagreed while 14 respondents (7.1 %) were undecided on the perception that the introduction of the E-tax filing system by the BIRS will build more confidence in taxpayers in Benue state thus boosting their morale to comply with their statutory obligation of paying taxes. Still on the same table, 83 respondents representing 42.3 % on item 9 strongly agreed, 45 respondents agreed, and 24 respondents disagreed while 19 respondents (9.7 %) strongly disagreed. On this same item, 25 respondents were undecided on the view that the E-tax filing is less prone to manipulations and its adoption will help curb tax evasion. Lastly, item 10 of the table indicates that 106 respondents representing 54.1 % strongly agreed, 59 respondents (30.1 %) agreed, while 14 respondents (7.1 %) disagreed with the statement. The respondents on the same item, 12 of them strongly disagreed while 5 were undecided on the statement that the E-filing introduced by Benue State Inland Revenue Serve (BIRS) has positive effect on tax compliance in Benue state.

Table 3: E- Portal System and Tax Compliance

No	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	UD	Total
11	The e-payment portal system introduced by the BIRS will help ease tax remittances.	78(39.8)	85(43.4)	5(2.6)	10(5.1)	18(9.2)	196
12	The e-payment portal system will enhance payment of taxes within the stipulated time range.	99(50.5)	77(39.3)	6(3.1)	4(2.0)	19(9.7)	196
13	The e-portal payment system will boost revenue generation since it is less prone to manipulations.	81(41.3)	87(44.4)	19(9.7)	7(3.6)	13(6.6)	196
14	E-portal system will allow for a consistent use of E-tax automation, which will provide useful information for evaluation of taxpayer's records over time.	105(53.6)	45(23)	18(9.2)	12(6.1)	16(8.2)	196
15	The e-payment portal system introduced by BIRS has improve tax compliance by SMEs.	89(45.4)	71(36.2)	23(11.7)	9(4.6)	4(2)	196

Total	452	367	71	40	63	980
Average	90.4	73.4	14.2	8.4	9	196

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 3 shows information on E-Payment Portal. From the table item 11 shows that out of 196 respondents, 78 respondents representing 39.8 % strongly agreed, 85 respondents (43.4%) agreed, 5 respondents (2.6 %) disagreed. Only 10 respondents representing 5.1 % further strongly disagreed while 18 respondents (9.2 %) were undecided on the view that the E-payment payment portal system introduced by BIRS will help ease tax remittances. On item 12, 99 respondents representing 50.5 % strongly agreed, 77 respondents (39.3 %) agreed, 6 respondents (3.1 %) disagreed. Also, 4 respondents (2 %) further strongly disagreed while 19 respondents representing 9.7 % were undecided on the view that the E-payment portal system will enhance payment of taxes within the stipulated time range.

Again, item 13 depicts that 81 respondents (41.3 %) strongly agreed, 87 respondents (44.4 %) agreed while 19 respondents disagreed. On the other hand, only 7 respondents representing 3.6 % strongly disagreed while 13 respondents (6.6 %) were undecided on the statement that the E-payment portal system will boost revenue generation since it is less prone to manipulations. Still on the same table, 105 respondents representing 53.6 % on item 14 strongly agreed, 45 respondents (23 %) agreed, and 18 respondents disagreed while 12 respondents strongly disagreed. More so, on this same item, 16 respondents (8.2 %) were undecided on the view that the E-portal system will allow for a consistent use of E-tax automation, which will provide useful information for evaluation of taxpayers' records over time. Finally, item 15 of the table indicates that 89 respondents representing 45.4 % strongly agree, 71 respondents (36.2 %) agree, while 23 respondents (11.7 %) disagree. The respondents on the same item, 9 (4.6 %) of them strongly disagree while 4 (2 %) were undecided on the statement that the E-payment portal system introduced by BIRS has improved tax compliance by SMEs in the state.

Table 4: TIN and Tax Compliance

No	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	UD	Total
16	TIN will enable tax authorities to easily access information about taxpayers and get hold of tax evaders.	75(38.3)	79(40.3)	14(7.4)	12(6.1)	9(4.6)	196
17	The information provided by TIN will serve better the need of a wider group of tax administrators as it provides a wider range of information about the taxpayers.	81(41.3)	88(44.9)	15(7.7)	8(4.1)	4(2)	196
18	The use of TIN by tax authorities in Nigeria will bring about more faithful records about taxpayers, thus encourage the taxpayers to comply.	91(46.4)	67(34.2)	20(10.2)	10(5.1)	8(4.1)	196
19	The benefit of accessing taxpayer's information across the three tiers of tax authorities through TIN will close loopholes for taxpayers to escape the tax net.	84(42.9)	92(47)	8(4.1)	3(1.5)	9(4.6)	196

20	TIN has impacted positively on taxpayers compliance	103(52.6)	64(32.7)	10(5.1)	6(3.1)	3(1.5)	196
	Total	434	390	67	39	33	980
	Average	86.8	78	13.4	7.8	6.6	196

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4 displays information on Taxpayers' Identification Number (TIN). From the table item 16 shows that out of 196 respondents, 75 respondents representing 38.3 % strongly agreed, 79 respondents (40.3 %) agreed, 14 respondents with percentage of 7.4 disagreed. About 12 respondents representing 6.1 % further strongly disagreed while 9 respondents were undecided on the view that the TIN will enable tax authorities to easily access information about taxpayers and get hold of tax evaders. On item 17, 81 respondents representing 41.3 % strongly agreed, 88 respondents (44.9 %) agreed, 15 respondents (7.7 %) disagreed while 8 respondents (4.1%) further strongly disagreed and 4 respondents (2 %) were undecided on the view that the information provided by TIN will serve better the need of a wider group of tax administrators as it provide a wider range of information about the taxpayers.

Furthermore, item 18 indicates that 91 respondents representing 46.4 % strongly agreed, 67 respondents (34.2 %) agreed while 20 respondents representing 10.2 % disagreed. However, 10 respondents (5.1 %) strongly disagreed while 8 respondents (4.1 %) were undecided on the statement that the use of TIN by tax authorities in Nigeria will bring about more faithful records about taxpayers, thus encourage the taxpayers to comply. From the same table on item19, out of 196 respondents 84 strongly representing 42.9 % agreed on the view that the benefit of accessing taxpayers' information across the three tiers of tax authorities through TIN will close loopholes for taxpayers to escape the tax net, 92 respondents (47 %) agreed to this assertion, 8 respondents (4.1%) disagreed while 3 respondents (1.5 %) strongly disagreed and 9 respondents (4.6 %) were undecided for the item. Finally, item 20 of the table indicates that 103 respondents representing 52.6 % strongly agreed, 64 respondents (32.7 %) agreed, while 10 respondents (5.1 %) disagreed. The respondents on the same item, 6 of them strongly disagreed while 3 were undecided on the statement that the TIN has impacted positively on taxpayers' compliance.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

Table 5: Summary of Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Observation	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
POS	196	4.1837	1.3386	1	5
EFS	196	4.1735	1.3962	1	5
EPP	196	4.2857	1.1094	1	5
TIN	196	3.5816	1.5684	1	5
TCOMP	196	3.3520	1.5895	1	5

Source: STATA version 13

The result of table 5 shows a total of 196 observations. This connotes the total number of respondents that were used in the study. The result shows there were four variables in the study, the dependent variable was the TCOMP while the independent variables were the POS, EFS, EPPS and TIN. Based on the descriptive statistics, the result proves that TCOMP

had the mean of 3.352 with a low standard deviation of 1.589 this implies that tax compliance using electronic tax system by SMEs in Benue State is high. This result points to the fact that if efforts are not relented, electronic tax system may witness unprecedented positive effect on tax compliance by SMEs in Benue State.

The descriptive statistic further shows that EPP has the highest mean of 4.286 among the independent variables with a low variability of 1.1094 while the minimum and maximum stand at 1.00 and 5.00 respectively. The POS, EFS and TIN have 4.184, 4.173 and 3.582 as their mean with variations of 1.339, 1.396 and 1.568, respectively. The maximum and minimum for all the independent variables stands at 1.00 and 5.00 respectively. This implies that majority of respondents agreed that POS has compliance with tax system while few respondents disagreed that POS has effect on the level of tax compliance. Also, the EFS of 4.173 indicate that many respondents agreed that EFS has high compliance on tax payment while a few disagreed with the assertion. Furthermore, the TIN of 3.581 indicates that more respondents agreed that TIN has a positive effect on tax compliance while a few respondents disagreed that TIN has effect on tax compliance.

4.3 Correlation Statistics

Table 6 indicates that the highest correlation amongst the independent variable is between EFS and TIN (0.6737) which is below 0.80 that is considered harmful for regression analysis. The correlation between EFS and POS is 0.077 that of EPP and POS is 0.2401 while the correlation between TIN and POS is 0.0614. This clearly shows that there is absence of multicollinearity problem amongst the predictor variables.

Table 6: Correlation Result

Variable	TCOMP	POS	EFS	EPP	TIN
TCOMP	1.0000				
POS	0.3280	1.0000			
EFS	0.2929	0.0766	1.0000		
EPP	-0.3000	0.2401	0.0413	1.0000	
TIN	0.3584	0.0614	0.6737	-0.0020	1.0000

Source: STATA version 13

4.3.1 Multicollinearity Test

It is important to recall that multicollinearity problem amongst the independent variables in a data set is an issue that is capable of denying the researcher the use of multiple regression as a major technique for data analysis. Multicollinearity problem posit when the independent variables are highly correlated in such a way that the effect of the separate explanatory variables cannot be felt on the dependent variable.

To further authenticate the absence of multicollinearity issues in the data set, the variance inflation factor specific estimation test was carried out to further confirm the absence of multicollinearity problems among the predictor variables; the result of the variance inflation factor test is shown below.

The result in table 7 shows that VIF of EFS is 1.90 that of TIN is 1.87, POS has a VIF of 1.10 and EPP has a VIF of 1.07. This result coupled with that of the correlation analysis authenticates that there is absence of multicollinearity among the independent variables. The average variance inflation factor among the predictor variables was 1.49 which is above 1 and below 10. Akpa (2015) opined that a VIF of above 1 and less than 10 is good enough to explain the absence of multicollinearity.

Table 7: VIF for Independent Variables

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
EFS	1.90	0.526
TIN	1.89	0.529
POS	1.10	0.908
EPP	1.07	0.932
Mean VIF	1.49	

Source: STATA version 13

4.3.2 Heteroskedasticity test

After the Ordinary Least Square regression was conducted on the dataset a heteroskedasticity test was done to check if the variability of the error terms was constant. The null hypothesis is that there is the presence of homoskedasticity however; the result of the Breusch-Pagan/Cook Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity shows a p-value of 0.0372 indicating the presence of heteroskedasticity implying that the error term does not have a constant variation. This is also a test that supports the use of multiple regression analyses, the result is shown in table 8.

Table 8: Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity

Test	value
Chi Square	4.34
Prob. > Chi ²	0.0372

4.3.3 The Multiple Regression Result

The table 9 shows that electronic tax system account for about 42.33 % of tax compliance by SMEs in Benue State if all other factors are not considered. This means that the effect of electronic tax system is a growing process that is yet to reach average level. It can also be seen that the probability of the F-statistics proves that the OLS model is fit for generalisation of the results obtained from the model based on the P-value of 0.000. The model is generally fit at 1% level of confidence; the F-value of 35.06 is an indication that all the variables are significantly different from zero and are suitable for generalisation of findings. Further evidence from table 9 shows that, POS has a positive (1.090) and significant (0.000) effect on tax compliance by SMEs in Benue State. EFS has a significant relationship with TCOMP of SMEs based on the p-value of 0.000. It also follows that EPP has a positive and significant effect with TCOMP based on the coefficient of 0.273 and a p-value of 0.007. The relationship

between TIN and TCMOP was not different as it witnessed a positive 0.585 coefficient with TCOMP and a significant association indicated by a p-value of 0.000.

Table 9: OLS Regression Result

VARIABLE	COEFF	T	P-Value
POS	1.090	3.90	0.000
EFS	-2.102	-7.92	0.000
EPP	0.273	2.75	0.007
TIM	0.585	4.56	0.000
R-SQR			0.423
Prob>F			0.000
F-Value			35.06

Source: STATA version 13

4.4 Test of Hypotheses

The hypotheses in this study were tested using the p-values derived from the OLS regression results, as shown in Table 9. The decision rule was to reject the null hypothesis if the p-value was less than 0.05, indicating statistical significance, and to accept it if the p-value was equal to or greater than 0.05. The hypotheses are addressed as follows:

H0₁: POS has no significant effect on tax compliance by SMEs in Benue State

The p-value for the POS variable is 0.000, which is less than the threshold of 0.05. This result indicates that there is a statistically significant effect of POS on tax compliance. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H0₁) is rejected, implying that the adoption of POS systems has a significant positive effect on tax compliance by SMEs in Benue State.

H0₂: E-filing has no significant effect on tax compliance by SMEs in Benue State

The p-value associated with the E-filing variable is 0.000, which is below 0.05, signifying statistical significance. As a result, the null hypothesis (H0₂) is rejected. This shows that the adoption of e-filing systems has a significant impact on tax compliance by SMEs in Benue State.

H0₃: E-portal payment system has no significant effect on tax compliance by SMEs in Benue State

The p-value for the E-portal payment (EPP) variable is 0.007, which is also less than 0.05. This means that there is a statistically significant relationship between the use of E-portal

payment systems and tax compliance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that E-portal payment systems positively influence tax compliance by SMEs in the state.

H0₄: The adoption of TIN has no significant effect on tax compliance by SMEs in Benue State

The p-value for the TIN variable is 0.000, which is well below the 0.05 threshold. This shows there is a significant relationship between the use of TIN and tax compliance by the SMEs. Consequently, the null hypothesis (H0₄) is rejected, and it is concluded that the implementation of TIN has a significant effect on improving tax compliance by SMEs in Benue State.

4.5 Discussion of Findings

Data was collected in order to determine the effect of electronic tax system on tax compliance by SMEs in Benue State. Below are the discussions based on the data analysed.

4.5.1 Point of Sale (POS) and Tax Compliance

The results of this study show that the POS system has a significant effect on tax compliance by SMEs in Benue State, with a p-value indicating a positive relationship. The introduction of POS systems appears to have made record-keeping easier and more accurate for small businesses, facilitating real-time transaction tracking and minimizing the complexities associated with traditional cash registers. This ease of access and transparency has likely contributed to better compliance rates as businesses find it easier to maintain accurate records of sales and tax remittances. The findings the current study agrees with Rosen (2015), who asserted that POS systems play a crucial role in enhancing transparency and compliance in tax administration by offering efficient transaction recording. This consistency suggests that the digitalization of payment systems like POS may offer a sustainable solution for improving tax compliance by SMEs, especially when supported by adequate infrastructure.

4.5.2 E-Filing System and Tax Compliance by SMEs

The result of this study shows that the E-filing system significantly affects tax compliance by SMEs in Benue State. The significant impact is likely due to the convenience and speed that E-filing provides, enabling businesses to submit returns and make payments without physical visits to tax offices. This convenience is particularly valuable for SMEs that need to manage time and resources effectively. The flexibility of the E-filing system, which accommodates various transactions such as claiming refunds and carrying forward tax losses, may contribute to higher compliance. This result is similar with the findings of Irefe-Esema and Akinmade (2020), who found that E-filing improved compliance rates among Nigerian SMEs by reducing the administrative burden and making tax processes more user-friendly. Similarly, Mugo (2019) observed in South Africa that E-filing increased timely tax submissions. These affirm that tax processes through E-filing can significantly improve compliance rates by SMEs.

4.5.3 Electronic Portal Payment (EPP) and Tax Compliance by SMEs

The findings of the current study reveal that the electronic portal payment system has a significant impact on tax compliance by SMEs in Benue State. The availability of online payment options has made it easier for businesses to remit taxes, thereby reducing the barriers associated with manual payment methods. This means that as more SMEs adopt electronic payment methods, compliance rates are likely to improve further. This is consistent with the perspective of the Federal Inland Revenue Services (2014), which emphasized the

role of electronic payment platforms in easing tax payment processes. It also agrees with the findings of Awai and Oboh (2020), who noted that the use of EPP systems contributed to reducing payment defaults by Nigerian SMEs.

4.5.4 Tax Identification Number (TIN) and Tax Compliance by SMEs

The results of this study show a significant relationship between the use of the Taxpayer Identification Number (TIN) and tax compliance by SMEs in Benue State. The TIN system facilitates accurate tracking of tax records, ensuring that businesses are properly registered and monitored by tax authorities. This improved record-keeping likely leads to better compliance as SMEs are aware of the transparency and accountability it entails. The findings are in agreement with those of Olurankinse and Oladeji (2018), who demonstrated that TIN implementation reduced fraudulent practices and increased tax compliance in Nigeria. Similarly, Adu-Gyamfi and Osei (2019) found that TIN systems in Ghana improved taxpayer registration and compliance by enhancing the traceability of tax records.

5.0 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examines the effect of electronic tax system on tax compliance by SMES in Benue State. This section of the study provides the summary of findings arising from the results. The part also presents the conclusion based on the findings in this study and makes recommendations and identifies the contribution to knowledge.

5.1 Summary

The study investigated the effect of electronic tax systems on tax compliance by small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Benue State, focusing on specific components such as Point of Sale (POS) systems, E-filing systems, Electronic Payment Portals (EPP), and the Tax Identification Number (TIN). The study used a structured questionnaire and semi-structured interviews to collect data from 196 respondents, including SMEs and tax officials from the Benue State Internal Revenue Service (BIRS). The findings revealed that electronic tax systems have a significant impact on tax compliance, accounting for 42.33% of the variations in compliance levels among SMEs. Specifically, the results demonstrated that POS, E-filing, EPP, and TIN each positively influence compliance levels, with p-values indicating statistically significant relationships. This shows that the digitalization of tax processes can improve transparency and ease of compliance, making tax administration more effective for both the authorities and the taxpayers in Benue State.

5.2 Conclusion

Based on the findings, it is concluded that the adoption of electronic tax systems has a substantial and positive effect on the compliance behavior of SMEs in Benue State. The study established that the introduction of POS systems, E-filing, EPP, and TIN has significantly enhanced the ease and efficiency of tax compliance. This is in agreement with the literature, which suggests that digital tax systems can simplify tax procedures, reduce the burden on taxpayers, and increase transparency. The findings imply that when tax systems are made more accessible and user-friendly through digital tools, compliance is likely to improve by SMEs in Benue State.

5.3 Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on the findings of this study:

- i. The Benue State Internal Revenue Service (BIRS) should enhance the user-friendliness of E-filing systems by developing a simpler application that facilitates registration, filing, and payment processes for SMEs. This can be achieved by offering step-by-step guides and improving user support services.
- ii. BIRS should intensify awareness campaigns to educate SMEs about the benefits and procedures involved in E-filing and using electronic payment portals. This will help bridge the knowledge gap and encourage more businesses to adopt these digital solutions, thereby increasing compliance rates.
- iii. The Benue State Government should consider subsidizing the cost of POS machines to make them more affordable for SMEs. This would enable more small businesses to adopt POS systems for tax payment, promoting a culture of transparency and accountability in tax compliance.
- iv. The government should also prioritize improving electricity supply and internet infrastructure in Benue State, which are critical for the smooth operation of EPP and other digital tax systems. This will ensure that businesses, particularly those in rural areas, can utilize electronic payment systems effectively.
- v. BIRS should also streamline the process for acquiring a TIN by reducing bureaucratic procedures, making it easier for SMEs to register and comply with tax regulations.

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